

Massué et al. (2025) – Data and Code Repository

This repository contains all raw data and R scripts associated with the manuscript:

Title: *Projected warming disrupts temperate serpulid communities, key engineers of benthic ecosystems: Evidence from in situ thermal experiments*

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I. Folder Structure and Contents

1. *Seasonal_pictures_analysis*

This folder contains final merged images of *in situ* experimental panels across three seasons (winter, spring, summer). Each cement slab (blue, stripe, white, yellow) was equipped with four heated panels representing four treatments: Control, Heatwave (H.W), +1°C, and +2°C.

Each PDF corresponds to one slab during one season and includes images merged from three consecutive monthly samplings. Panels appear in the following order: Month 1, Month 2, Month 3.

Annotation key (coloured circles around individual tubeworms):

- Red: Present only in one month
- Orange: Present in Month 1 and 2
- Yellow: Present in Month 2 and 3
- Green: Present across all three months

Only individuals present in the final month are numbered and tracked over time.

2. *Seasonal_excel_data*

Excel spreadsheets per season containing all raw data, including tubeworm identifications and ecological indices. Columns are labelled by slab colour (B = Blue, S = Stripe, W = White, Y = Yellow) and treatment (C = Control, D = Heatwave, 1 = +1°C, 2 = +2°C). Sheets include:

- Raw counts – Each row represents an individual. IDs match the numbered individuals in the annotated PDFs. Morphospecies are indicated numerically; “L” and “1-L” denote late settlement-stage individuals, either unidentified or tentatively identified. Bold-framed individuals were used for size and growth analysis.
- Proportion – Number and percentage of individuals per morphospecies and late-settlement stage worms (larvae), per cement slab (CROP) and per treatment (DOT = H.W), during the last month (M3).
- Size and growth measured – Number of individuals measured over time, per cement slab and per treatment, for each morphospecies.

- Size and growth analysis – The middle box represents the size in pixels of all final merged pictures per month, as well as the average size per season and across all seasons. This last average was used to convert pixel size into millimetres, based on the known size of the heated panel (98 mm). Size measurements over time were then used to calculate growth rates.
- Survival analysis – Survival percentage was calculated by determining how many individuals that settled during the first month were still present in the last month (indicated with green circles).
- Recruitment analysis – Recruitment was calculated differently for each month. For month one, it corresponds to the total number of worms present in the first month (red 1). For month two, it includes the worms that appeared only in month two (red 2), as well as those present in both month two and month three (yellow). For month three, it includes only the worms newly present in month three (red 3).
- Percentage cover analysis – Percentage cover per individual was calculated separately for late-settlement stage worms (red 1, 2, 3) and early-settlement stage worms (orange, yellow, green), due to their significant size differences (previously determined in the Survival analysis). The average worm size per month (for all measured individuals) was converted into circular surface area to estimate their coverage. An average surface area for larvae was also calculated separately and added to the total percentage cover.

3. Data_sets

Cleaned .csv files prepared for statistical analysis. These are the data used to generate the results reported in the manuscript.

4. R_codes_and_Functions

R scripts used to process the data and generate statistical mixed linear models and figures presented in the manuscript. Includes custom functions.

II. Contact

For questions regarding the data, code, or to request access to high-resolution final merged images (total 97 GB), please contact:

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